

ANALYSIS OF PHILIPPINE GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE ON EDUCATION AND GDP GROWTH

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Analysis of Philippine Government Expenditure on Education and GDP Growth

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Abstract

The paper investigates the relationship between government expenditure on education (GEE) and the gross domestic product (GDP) in the Philippines using time series data from 2000 to 2021. The study seeks to examine the nature and direction of cointegration between government expenditure on education and economic growth to substantiate the theory of Keynesian's hypothesis and Wagner's law that public spending generates national income and national income drives government expenditures, respectively. The econometric method employed was the cointegration using Engle-Granger and Phillips-Ouliaris tests and error correction technique. Based on the Engle-Granger and Phillips-Ouliaris tests, results revealed that gross domestic product and government expenditure on education are cointegrated. In estimating the long-run and short-run Run Models, both the long-run model and the short-run model are appropriate for GDP and GEE.

Keywords: *cointegration, education, government expenditure, gdp, and relationship*

Introduction

Education is crucial for the nation's economic development. Education helps to advance the labor force and increase worker productivity, resulting in increased national output (Hua, 2016) and economic growth (Ahamefule, 2018).

In the study conducted by Tomic (2015) on the impact of Public Education Expenditure on Economic growth in the European Union and for Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa (BRICS), he argued the significant impact of education expenditure on the country's income. That indeed, education is a factor for growth with a 0.000 p- value at a 5% confidence level.

According to the state-run Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS), public spending per student in primary and secondary education is lower than in other Asia Pacific nations (Simeon, 2022). Additionally, education spending in the country climbed from 5.8 percent in 2005 to 7.5 percent in 2019. Meanwhile, expenditure on education in the country in 2021 increased by 1.07 percent from 2020 to 16.62 percent (Macrotrends, 2023).

The Government Basic Education Act of 2001 or Republic Act No. 9155 or an act instituting a framework of governance for basic education, establishing authority and accountability, renaming the department of education, culture, and sports as the department of education, and for other purposes was established to ensure that all Filipino children receive free, obligatory elementary and high school education and to defend and advance the right to a quality basic education for everyone (Official Gazette, 2001).

In 2017, the Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act was signed by President Rodrigo Duterte, which requires the government to fund free tertiary education for all Filipino citizens at all state universities and colleges (SUCs). Around 1.6 million Filipino students will no longer be required to pay tuition and other fees as of 2021 through the government's Free Higher Education program (Rocamora, 2021).

On the one hand, according to Keynes (1936) as cited by Udo and Effiong (2014), government expenditure is viewed as an exogenous variable that may be used as a policy instrument to affect economic growth. Further, according to Wagner (1993), government expenditure is perceived as a result or an outcome rather than a cause of increases in national revenue. Thus, the study investigates the nature and direction of causality between government expenditures on education and GDP and the relationship between these macroeconomic variables. Understanding the direction of causality between these two variables becomes essential for policymaking (Singh and Sahni, 1984).

In addition, according to Larocque (2008), education, particularly at the tertiary level, directly and indirectly supports economic growth. It increases worker productivity and fosters the development of new ideas, technologies, and information. Which an essential tool for a government to manage the economy is public spending (Torruam, Chiawa, and Abur, 2014),

Thus, the purpose of this paper is to empirically examine the relationship between government expenditure on education (GEE) and the gross domestic product (GDP) in the Philippines using time series data from 2000 to 2021 and determine the direction of cointegration between the two variables. Because policymakers may be able to establish and implement appropriate policies that could aid the nation's development in economic and educational planning if they have a proper grasp of the relationship between public expenditure on education and economic growth.

However, the study has limitations in terms of its sample frame because it only contains the time series data from 2000–2021 because those are the only statistics for Government Expenditure on Education that are currently accessible. Meanwhile, the research gap to be filled in some of the literature is the failure to estimate and provide the long- run and short-run models in cointegration analysis which will be shown in this paper.

On the other hand, this study is anchored on Sustainable Development Goal no. 4, Quality Education, which promotes lifelong learning to all.

Research Questions

This research study sought answers to the following:

1. Determine the stationarity of the two variables; and
2. Examine the cointegrating relationship between government expenditure on education (GEE) and the Philippines' gross domestic product (GDP).

Methodology

Research Design

The quantitative empirical research method was used in the study, employing cointegration analysis and error correction technique to empirically examine the relationship between the government expenditures on education (GEE) and gross domestic Product (GDP) in the Philippines and the direction of its cointegrating relationship.

Further, using the Eviews software, the study used the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test unit root tests to check if the variables in question were stationary (this answers objective number 1). That, if the prob. value of the ADF test statistic is less than 0.05, then we reject the null hypothesis that the variable has a unit root, meaning the variable is significantly stationary. Moreover, in testing cointegration between the two variables, Engle and Granger using the ADF approach and Philips Ouliaris Cointegration Test using P. Perron approach were conducted. Also, to estimate its long-run model (this answers objective no. 2). On the other hand, the Error Correction Model was used to estimate its short-run model. By using cointegration and ECM, this examines whether any changes in the short run will affect the long run.

Source of Data

The study used secondary data particularly the annual time series data from 2000 to 2021 for government expenditure on education (GEE) and the Philippines' gross domestic product (GDP) drawn from the World Bank.

Model Specification

It is ideal for creating a model to support the relationship that exists between the variables when attempting to ascertain the effect of government expenditures on education on economic growth in the Philippines.

The Wagner's law method asserts that national income drives government expenditures, and the Keynesian approach contends that public spending generates national income and serves as the foundation for this study's framework.

Consequently, the following is the long-run and short-run model for this study:

Long-run model:

$$\ln \text{GDP}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln \text{GEE}_t + \epsilon_t$$

where $\beta_1 > 0$ from classical theory are parameters to be estimated

$\ln \text{GDP}_t$ = log Gross Domestic Product

$\ln \text{GEE}_t$ = log Government Expenditure on Education

ϵ_t = Stationary error term.

Short-run model:

where:

$$\Delta \text{GDP}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Delta \text{GEE}_t + \beta_2 \epsilon_{t-1} + \nu_t$$

ECT = Error Correction Term ($\beta_2 \epsilon_{t-1}$)

β_2 = Error Correction Term estimated coefficient, where

$$-1 < \beta_2 < 0$$

Results and Discussion

Checking for Stationarity (Objective No. 1):

As shown in Figure 1, $\ln \text{GDP}$ and $\ln \text{GEE}$ have the same trend and are moving upward together but are evidently seen to have

spuriousness.

Figure 1. Graphical Presentation showing the Trend between GDP and GEE

In addition, as shown in the correlogram result for lnGDP and lnGEE, it shows a decaying pattern indicating non-stationarity. Hence, a formal test using a unit root test was conducted to verify the result.

Unit Root Tests

Figure 2 shows the results regarding the order of integration of the series using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test for the lnGDP at level.

Null Hypothesis: LNGDP has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=4)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.791685	0.0109
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.831511	
5% level	-3.029970	
10% level	-2.655194	

Figure 2. ADF test statistic result for lnGDP – at level

Based on the result above, the prob. value of the ADF test statistic is significant at 0.0109, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis that lnGDP has a unit root. Thus, the series is stationary.

Meanwhile, Figure 3 shows the result regarding the order of integration of the series using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test for the GEE at level.

Null Hypothesis: LNGEE has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=4)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.468604	0.5293
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.788030	
5% level	-3.012363	
10% level	-2.646119	

Figure 3. ADF test statistic result for lnGEE – At level

Based on the result, the prob. value of the ADF test statistic is not significant at 0.5293, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, we fail to reject the null hypothesis that lnGEE has a unit root. Thus, the series is non-stationary, and there is a need to test the 1st difference.

Figure 4 now represents a significant ADF test statistic with a prob. value of 0.0181, which is now less than a 0.05 significance level. Hence, lnGEE is now stationary, and we now reject the null hypothesis. LnGEE now has no unit root.

Null Hypothesis: D(LNGEE) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=4)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.361043	0.0004
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.808546	
5% level	-3.020686	
10% level	-2.650413	

Figure 4. ADF test statistic result for lnGEE – using 1st Difference Now, both the lnGDP and lnGEE are no longer spurious but stationary

Estimate Long Run Model

Dependent Variable: LNGDP
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 05/25/23 Time: 10:15
 Sample: 2000 2021
 Included observations: 21

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2.014255	1.603379	-1.256256	0.2243
LNGEE	1.338507	0.585583	2.285766	0.0339

R-squared	0.215677	Mean dependent var	1.646636
Adjusted R-squared	0.174397	S.D. dependent var	0.380501
S.E. of regression	0.345733	Akaike info criterion	0.804094
Sum squared resid	2.271097	Schwarz criterion	0.903572
Log likelihood	-6.442987	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.825683
F-statistic	5.224728	Durbin-Watson stat	2.089931
Prob(F-statistic)	0.033927		

Figure 5. Long Run model for lnGDP and lnGEE

Based on the model above, the lnGEE has a significant prob. value with less than 0.05 significance level. Showing that there is a relationship between gross domestic product and government expenditure on education. It also shows that a 1% increase in the GEE, will also increase GDP by 1.34%. This indicates a long-run regression. However, based on the theory of Granger, if $R^2 >$ Durbin-Watson Statistic, it indicates spurious regression. Hence, based on the model, R^2 is less than d , which denotes that the model is not spurious.

Test for Cointegration (Objective No. 2):

To test the cointegration of GDP and GEE, we estimate the equation using the Engle and Granger and Philips Ouliaris Cointegration tests.

Results revealed that in the cointegration equation, the GEE p-value is significant at 0.0339, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance (See Figure 6). Thus, GDP and GEE have a long-term relationship. Further, prob. values for both Engle-Granger and Phillips-Ouliaris tests are significant. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis that the GDP and GEE series are not cointegrated (see Table 1).

Dependent Variable: LNGDP
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 05/25/23 Time: 10:15
 Sample: 2000 2021
 Included observations: 21

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2.014255	1.603379	-1.256256	0.2243
LNGEE	1.338507	0.585583	2.285766	0.0339

R-squared	0.215677	Mean dependent var	1.646636
Adjusted R-squared	0.174397	S.D. dependent var	0.380501
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Log likelihood	-6.442987	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.825683
F-statistic	5.224728	Durbin-Watson stat	2.089931
Prob(F-statistic)	0.033927		

Figure 6. Cointegration Equation

Table 1. Engle and Granger and Philips Ouliaris Cointegration Results

Engle and Granger Test	p-value
Engle-Granger tau-statistic	0.0168
Engle-Granger z-statistic	0.0116
Philips Ouliaris Test	
Phillips-Ouliaris tau-statistic	0.0134
Phillips-Ouliaris z-statistic	0.0113

Error Correction Model Estimate Short Run Model

Based on the result in the short-run model for lnGDP and lnGEE, the coefficient estimate for residuals is significant at -0.970470 and did satisfy the rule of thumb $-1 < ECT < 0$. Further, their p-values for $D(\lnGEE)$ and Residuals are also significant at 0.0451 and 0.0011, respectively. Such that for a 1% increase in the GEE, GDP will increase by 2%.

Dependent Variable: D(LNGDP)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 05/25/23 Time: 10:22
 Sample (adjusted): 2001 2019
 Included observations: 19 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.000703	0.084426	-0.008326	0.9935
D(LNGEE)	2.300207	1.058447	2.173190	0.0451
RESIDUALS_LT(-1)	-0.970470	0.244986	-3.961333	0.0011

R-squared	0.592103	Mean dependent var	0.017563
Adjusted R-squared	0.541116	S.D. dependent var	0.539453
S.E. of regression	0.365430	Akaike info criterion	0.968457
Sum squared resid	2.138629	Schwarz criterion	1.117579
Log likelihood	-6.200342	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.993694
F-statistic	11.61281	Durbin-Watson stat	1.907447
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000766		

Figure 7. Short Run model for lnGDP and lnGEE

Long Run and Short Run Estimated Models (Objective no. 3):

The long-run model for lnGDP and lnGEE is shown below: $\ln GDP_t = -2.014255 + 1.338507 \ln GEE_t + \epsilon_t$

The short-run model for lnGDP and lnGEE is shown below: $\ln GDP_t = -0.0000703 + 2.300207 \ln GEE_t - 0.970470 \epsilon_{t-1} + \nu_t$

Thus, in the estimated models above, there we can see a discrepancy of lnGEE from 1.338507 in the long-run model to 2.300207 in the short-run model. Suggesting that almost 10% of the discrepancy between the long run and the short run is corrected within a year.

Table 2. Comparison of Long Run and Short Run Estimated Models

Variable	Model			
	Long Run	p-value	Short Run	p-value
C	-2.014255	0.2243	-0.0000703	0.9935
GEEt	1.338507	0.0339	2.300207	0.0451
ECT	n/a	n/a	-0.970470	0.0011

Based on Table 2, both the Long Run Model and Short Run Model have significant p-values of GEE, further, for ECT (only for the short- run model) with less than a 0.05 significance level. Therefore, both the long-run and short-run models are appropriate for GDP and GEE.

Conclusions

Results revealed that gross domestic product (GDP) is stationary at level and government expenditure on education (GEE) is stationary at 1st difference. Moreover, based on the Engle-Granger and Phillips-Ouliaris tests, GDP and GEE are cointegrated.

In estimating the Long Run and Short Run Models, results revealed that both the long-run model and the short-run model are appropriate for GDP and GEE. Hence, any changes in the short run will affect the long run.

Consequently, it is believed that when the country has a higher GDP, it may have more money and resources available for education. In this regard, education is important for the country’s economic growth. That a unit increase in GEE will also increase the GDP, which, if a government increases its spending, particularly in education, will have a multiplier effect on economic growth. Such that based on the findings, a 1% increase in the GEE contributes to a 1.34% increase in GDP per capita in the long run. While, in terms of the short-run relationship between GDP and GEE, with a 1% increase in the GEE, GDP will increase by 2%.

In the case of GDP and government expenditure on education in the Philippines for time series data from 2000-2021, the result supports the theory of Wagner and the Keynesian approach, which contends that public spending generates national income or GDP since results revealed cointegration between the two variables. Due to the fact that education promotes labor force development and increases worker productivity, the effect will be felt over time, contributing to increased economic growth and national output.

On the other hand, this study may contribute to the existing literature on the relationship between government expenditure on education and GDP, specifically focusing on the Philippine context, thereby informing policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders involved in education and economic planning.

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